

ARCHITECTURE

CROSS-CULTURAL SIGNIFICANCE OF RELIGIOUS MONUMENTS IN THE ARCHITECTURE OF ISLAM AND CHRISTIANITY: HISTORICAL AND MODERN APPROACHES

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Abstract

In this article, we will explore various aspects of religious architecture and its cross-cultural significance. We will talk about Islamic and Christian architectural styles, aesthetic and symbolic features of these places, as well as their historical development. The temples of each religion reflect the historical and cultural heritage of the societies in which they were built. The article will also discuss how religious architecture has developed in modern times and how today's architects approach religious buildings. Humans have sought to find the source of their existence since the dawn of time, and the quest to find this beginning has given rise to the need to believe in and worship a creator. To show their loyalty to the Creator, people who worship began to build temples to perform their worship. These places of worship are among the first examples of architectural structures. In the process of construction, there is a traditional style in places of worship of all religions, whether human or divine. Cathedrals, one of Christianity's places of worship, can have different architectural designs and reflect the influence of different eras and styles. Inside the cathedrals, there are works of art such as mosaics, frescoes, stained glass windows and sculptures that often attract the attention of visitors. Places of worship in Islam are large domed mosques, minarets, spacious courtyards, brightly colored embroidery with geometric shapes and repeating patterns, and mihrabs that always face Mecca. In mosques, more importance is given to internal beauty and aesthetics than external appearance.

Keywords: Religious architecture, Islamic architecture, Christian architecture, Mosques, Churches

Introduction

Religious architecture has occupied an important place in human history for millennia and has reflected the spiritual values and aesthetic principles of each religion. Religious buildings are not only places of worship, but also important examples of architecture and art history. Religious architecture includes buildings and structures built to express spiritual and religious beliefs in different periods of history and cultures. This architectural style is reflected in the design of religious places of worship, shrines, temples and other sacred places. Religious architecture not only creates a space, but also visually expresses the religious and spiritual content of that place.

Religious architecture is one of the most important forms of architecture that reflects people's beliefs and spirituality. Each culture has its own style of religious architecture, and these styles show great diversity depending on the historical and cultural context. Religious architecture, besides being the pinnacle of aesthetic and engineering skills, also serves as a window into the spiritual world of people. Each work in this field is valuable and unique as an architectural expression of the spiritual experience and faith of humanity. Islamic and Christian religious architectures have different styles and elements that reflect the aesthetic and religious principles of both religions.

Islamic architecture is an architectural style that developed with the spread of Islamic culture and religion and is known for its unique style and design features in different regions. Islamic architecture includes various building types such as mosques, madrasahs, tombs, palaces, and baths. Key features of

Islamic architecture include elements such as geometric patterns, arabesque motifs, calligraphy and large interior spaces.

Main part

The best examples of famous Islamic architectural monuments are Masjid al-Haram, Masjid-i-Nabawi, Alhambra. It represents the rich and varied heritage of Islamic architecture and each has its own beauty and architectural styles.

Masjid al-Haram

It is a large mosque located in Mecca and surrounds the Kaaba, the holiest mosque in Islam. Its architecture and history are of great importance because this mosque is the spiritual center of the Islamic world. The history of Masjid al-Haram goes back to pre-Islamic times. The Kaaba, according to Islamic beliefs, was first built by Prophet Abraham and his son Ismail. With the emergence and spread of Islam, Masjid al-Haram expanded and developed. The Kaaba, located in the center of Masjid al-Haram and to which all Muslims face the qibla during prayer, was the holiest place in Islam. Every side of the Kaaba is decorated with special verses and prayers. There is a wide area around Masjid al-Haram. This area is intended for pilgrims and visitors to worship and perform Tawaf (circumventing the Kaaba seven times). The foundation of the Kaaba is made of marble, and the building is made of granite. Its height is 13.1 meters, and its area is 142 square meters. The four corners of the Kaaba are arranged according to the main directions of the world. Hajar-ul-Aswad (Black Stone) located in the eastern corner, 1.5 meters above the ground, is protected in a special silver frame. The door in the east of the building

is 2.5 meters high and made of 280 kilograms of pure gold. The Kaaba is of great importance for Muslims as both the center of worship and the direction of the Qibla.

The inner space of Masjid al-Haram is large and spacious, supported by many columns. This large space allows thousands of people to worship at the same time. There is a huge Clock Tower located near Masjid al-Haram, which also serves as a hotel and gives the mosque a special look. Masjid al-Haram has many minarets. These minarets are used for azan (call to prayer) and surround the mosque. Masjid al-Haram has several domes that cover the vast interior of the mosque and improve its acoustic properties. In the interior and exterior decoration of Masjid al-Haram, fine geometric patterns typical of Islamic architecture and calligraphic inscriptions full of verses from the Koran are widely used. The floors and walls of the mosque are made of high-quality marble and decorated with gold, which gives it a magnificent and divine appearance. Throughout history, Masjid al-Haram has been expanded and rebuilt several times. These expansions

were made to accommodate the increased number of visitors, especially during the Hajj. In recent years, major projects implemented by the government of Saudi Arabia have significantly increased the capacity of the mosque.

Masjid al-Haram, as the holiest place for Muslims, has spiritual and cultural significance. Every year, millions of Muslims come here for Hajj and Umrah.

Masjid al-Haram, as the heart and center of Islam, symbolizes the unity and faith of Muslims.

This mosque is one of the most important examples of Islamic architecture and cultural heritage, and its historical and aesthetic values are passed down from generation to generation.

Masjid al-Haram is the most important place in the Islamic world with its magnificent architecture and deep spiritual significance. Its history and design reflect the richness and sanctity of Islamic culture. Currently, the area of Masjid al-Haram is 361,000 m². Jabir Bin Abdullah narrates that the Prophet said: One prayer in Masjid al-Haram is better than a hundred prayers [1

A late XIX century sketch of Mecca [1] 2008

Masjid-i-Nabawi

Masjid-i-Nabawi is one of the holiest mosques in the Islamic world and is located in Medina. This mosque is of special importance because it is the place where Prophet Muhammad lived and was buried. Its architecture has gone through several stages of expansion and reconstruction over time and has gained its present magnificence.

The first building, the Mosque, was built by Prophet Muhammad in the first year of Hijra (622). The first building was a simple structure. It had mud brick walls and columns made of palm tree trunks, and the ceiling was made of palm leaves. Umayyad period mosque was enlarged and rebuilt in a more solid structure with stone and brick during the reign of the Umayyad caliph Walid I (705-715 AD). The Abbasid caliphs also expanded the mosque and added new elements to it. During the Ottoman Empire, especially Sultan Suleiman the Magnificent and Sultan Mahmud II, the mosque was further expanded and rebuilt.

During the kingdom of present-day Saudi Arabia, the mosque was reconstructed on a large scale and equipped with modern technologies. The capacity of the mosque has been increased to a level capable of receiving millions of visitors. Masjid-i-Nabawi is known for its large green dome and fourteen minarets. The green dome is located above the Prophet's tomb and has a special significance. Minarets surround the

mosque and are used for the call to prayer. The large prayer area of the mosque allows thousands of Muslims to pray at the same time. The interior is supported by columns and covered with rich decorations. Holy places inside the mosque are the tombs of Prophet Muhammad, the tombs of Hazrat Abu Bakr and Hazrat Omar. These places are especially visited and are the most sacred areas of the mosque.

Rawdah al-Mutahhara (Garden of the Clean) located between the Prophet's tomb and the minbar, this area is considered a garden of paradise, and praying here is of great importance. In the interior and exterior decoration of the mosque, fine geometric patterns typical of Islamic architecture and calligraphic inscriptions full of verses from the Koran are widely used. The floors and walls of the mosque are decorated with high-quality marble and mosaics, which gives it a magnificent and divine appearance.

Lighting and ventilation systems equipped with modern technologies create a comfortable worship environment inside the mosque. Masjid-i-Nabawi has great spiritual and religious importance for Muslims. Praying here is considered more virtuous than worshipping in other mosques. Every year, millions of visitors visit this mosque during Hajj and Umrah and pray here. Masjid-i-Nabawi is one of the most important monuments not only of the Islamic world, but also of the world cultural heritage. Its architecture

and history reflect the richness of Islamic culture and religious values.

When the Prophet entered Medina at that time Yathrib, he told him to release the rider of his camel in order to determine the place where he would stay, and said that he would build a mosque and a house for himself in the place where the camel would lie down. The camel collapsed on the land belonging to two orphan brothers named Sahl and Suheil. The Prophet bought that field for a symbolic amount. All Muslims, including the Prophet himself, started building the mosque [4].

The dimensions of the mosque were 30.5 m x 35.62 m. The roof, supported by palm trunks, is made of beaten clay and palm leaves. It was 3.60 m tall. The three gates of the mosque were Bab-el-Rahma in the south, Bab-ul-Jibril in the west and Babel-Nisa in the east. After the battle of Khyber, the mosque was "expanded". The mosque extended 47.32 m on each

side, and three rows of columns were built near the western wall, which became the place of worship [5].

The second caliph Omar demolished all the houses around the mosque, except for Muhammad's wives, in order to expand the mosque. The dimensions of the new mosque were 57.49 m x 66.14 m. Sun-dried mud bricks were used to build the garden walls. In addition to sprinkling gravel on the floor, the height of the roof was increased to 5.6 m. Umar also built three more gates for the entrance. He also added Al-Butayha for people to recite poetry.

The third caliph Osman demolished the mosque in 649. It took 10 months to build a new rectangular mosque in Mecca with its face turned to the Kaaba. The dimensions of the new mosque were 81.40 m x 62.58 m. The number and names of the doors remained the same. The walls of the housing are made of stones laid with mortar. The palm trunk columns were replaced by stone columns connected by iron clamps. Teak wood was used in the reconstruction of the ceiling [5].

Al-Masjid an-Nabawi during the Ottoman Era, XIX century 2024

Alhambra

The Alhambra is a palace complex located in Granada, Spain, and one of the most magnificent examples of medieval Islamic architecture. The construction of the Alhambra Palace began in 1232 during the reign of Muhammad Bin Nasr, the Emir of the Emirate of Granada. Built by the Nasrid dynasty in the 13th century, this monument is considered one of the pinnacles of Islamic architecture. The Alhambra was used as both a defensive fortress and a royal palace, and its magnificent architecture reflects rich cultural and religious influences. The first builder was Muhammad I, and the palace complex was expanded and developed by subsequent sultans. During the Nasrid period, the Alhambra became one of the high points of Islamic architecture and art. The Alhambra complex contains various palaces, courtyards, gardens and mosques. The composition is symmetrically and functionally designed. The main palace complex consists of three parts: Mexuar, Comares Palace and the Palace of Lions.

Mekuar is one of the main spaces used for administrative work. The Mexuar Hall located here is decorated with beautiful mosaics, stalactites and decorative elements. This part is also known for its courtrooms and reception rooms.

Comares Palace is one of the most magnificent examples of Nasrid architecture. The Hall of Envoys, located here, is the largest room in the complex and is known for its rich decorations. The ceiling and walls

are decorated with rich patterns and epigraphic inscriptions.

Levakler Palace takes its name from the famous Levakler Fountain located in its courtyard. The fountain is known for the twelve lavak sculptures located around it and is one of the most beautiful elements of the palace. The courtyard of the palace is surrounded by slender pillars and designed to create wide open spaces.

The Alhambra is also famous for its gardens and moats. The Generalife Gardens are one of the most spectacular parts of the complex and are decorated with water channels, fountains and large green areas. These gardens have aesthetic and functional elements that reflect the Islamic concept of paradise. The Alhambra is one of the finest examples of Islamic art, with widely used calligraphic inscriptions and geometric patterns. Verses and poems from the Koran are among the main elements that decorate the walls. The walls and floors of the complex are decorated with rich mosaics and brickwork. These elements increase the visual richness and aesthetics of the architecture. The Alhambra has taken its place in the pages of history as one of the finest and most magnificent examples of Islamic architecture. Its rich history, aesthetic value and engineering features make it an important work to study and appreciate in the fields of architecture and art.

The Alhambra contains many inscriptions, most of which contain writings, poems and religious statements from the Koran. These inscriptions are written in classical Arabic and mainly aim to emphasize the

aesthetic beauty of the palace and reflect the Islamic culture. Most of the inscriptions were written by poets who lived in XIV century. Edgar Pisani, former president of the Institut du Monde Arabe (Institute of the Arab World) in Paris, describes the palace as one of the highest peaks that Islamic culture has brought to humanity, saying that the Alhambra is: A view from the Lion Garden.

Andalusian Islamic art cannot be considered separately from the history of Muslim Spain. When building the Alhambra, nothing was left to chance, every detail was carefully calculated. It is possible to understand this in the division of arches, in the appropriate placement of odd and even columns, in the perfect position of door and window locations. Thanks to this, magnificent perspectives have emerged, sunlight, water flow and the play of shadows have come

together between the courtyards and the open halls, providing an incredible harmony and elegance with the outside world. It is a high elegance that gives a feeling of delicacy that breaks and crumbles when touched. To truly understand the Alhambra, you need to understand and read the many inscriptions inside the palace. These inscriptions, which are carved with verses taken from the Koran and verses of Ibn-i Zamrak and other Muslim poets, completely cover some walls and stretch along the arches, door frames and column techniques. So it is almost impossible to separate these inscriptions from decorative motifs. Today, the Alhambra represents one of the most famous and impressive examples of Islamic architectural heritage in Europe. Due to its cultural importance, it has been declared a World Heritage Site by UNESCO since 1984 (UNESCO World Heritage Center, 1992) [12]

Al-Hambra, 1860 2024

Christian Architecture

Christian architecture has gone through many stages of development throughout its history. This development is closely related to the spread of Christian beliefs, the increase of religious functions and the advancement of architectural technologies. Churches and cathedrals occupy a special place in Christian architecture. Although churches were of simple structure during the early Christian era, large and elegant buildings in the Gothic style began to be built in the Middle Ages. These buildings are decorated with high ceilings, large windows and stained glass windows. Notable Christian monuments include Notre Dame Cathedral (Paris), Sagrada Familia (Barcelona) and St. Peter's Basilica (Vatican City).

Notre Dame Cathedral

Notre Dame Cathedral is a Gothic masterpiece located in the heart of Paris and considered a pearl of world architecture. This cathedral, which began construction in 1163 and lasted nearly two centuries, is known for its richness of architectural details and for displaying the highest levels of religious art. Notre Dame Cathedral is characterized by a large and lofty nave. This nave, one of the main features of the Gothic style, not only creates a large space inside the cathedral, but also attracts attention with its high ceilings and slender columns. This height and width is specially designed to make worshipers feel closer to God. One of its most striking elements is its famous flower windows. These windows are decorated with stained glass of different colors and provide great lighting.

These windows, located on the north, south and west facades, depict both religious scenes and historical events. Beam-supported girders used in cathedral architecture are one of the most important innovations of the Gothic style. These girders support the high walls of the building, making it possible for it to rise upwards. Thus, it was possible to reduce the thickness of the walls and make room for large windows. There are many reliefs and sculptures on the facade and interior of Notre Dame Cathedral. These sculptures and reliefs depict religious themes and saints. In particular, the three portals on the western facade are filled with richly decorated reliefs that depict stories from the Bible. The western facade of the cathedral attracts attention with two large towers. These towers are important both from the point of view of symmetry and aesthetics. The large rose window and three portals in the center of the facade are one of the best examples of the Gothic style. These portals are decorated with reliefs depicting religious scenes and saints. The interior of the cathedral is as impressive as the exterior. Here, different colored stained-glass windows, high ceilings and finely carved columns attract attention. The statues and bas-reliefs inside the cathedral enhance the spiritual atmosphere of the cathedral. Notre Dame Cathedral has undergone various restorations and repairs throughout history. In particular, a large-scale restoration was carried out by the French architect Eugène Viollet-le-Duc in XIX century. These restoration works were carried out with the aim of preserving and restoring the original architectural features of the cathedral. Notre Dame

Cathedral is one of the most magnificent architectural works not only of Paris, but of the whole world. Millions of tourists flock to this cathedral every year to see its rich architectural details and religious artwork. The pinnacle of Gothic style, this cathedral continues to amaze people for centuries. The church became a new worship center in April 1802. Some necessary renovations were carried out very quickly, and thus in December 1804, Napoleon Bonaparte was proclaimed Emperor of France in the presence of Pope Pius VII. For this occasion, the building was first painted and then decorated by Persie and Fontaine [6].

During the restoration of peace, the condition of the church was very bad, so the city administration was thinking of stopping the activity of the church completely. Fascinated by the structure of the church,

Victor Hugo wrote the novel "Notre-Dame de Paris" and this novel gained great fame. The main purpose of writing this novel was to increase attention to the church.

A fire appears to have occurred at Notre Dame between 1235 and 1240. History is silent on the matter, but it appears to be based on Viollet-le-Duc, where the fire caused serious damage. According to him, due to the hasty repair work, rose windows, flying buttresses and other structural details were mercilessly sacrificed [7, p. 8]. In 1862, the Notre-Dame Cathedral became part of the Historical Monument, and in 1991, UNESCO included the building in the list of world heritage [8, p. 5].

Notre-Dame de Paris, Western Façade

(Source: Smith, R. 1884, p.74.) *Notre-Dame de Paris, 2023*

Sagrada Família

The Sagrada Família is a magnificent basilica in Barcelona, Spain, built under the direction of Antoni Gaudí. Construction of the cathedral began in 1882 and is currently still unfinished, making it one of the longest-running buildings in the world. Gaudí's approach to modernity and nature-inspired architecture makes this basilica unique and awe-inspiring. The construction of the Sagrada Família began in 1882 and the chief architect of the project was Francesc de Paula del Villar. But a year later, Antoni Gaudí took over the project and completely redesigned it. Gaudí dedicated the last 15 years of his life only to the construction of this basilica. After Gaudí's death in 1926, construction continued and continues today. The Sagrada Família is the most striking example of the Catalan Modernisme style. This style is characterized by organic shapes, intricate mosaics and decorative details inspired by nature. Gaudí tried to create an architectural language in this basilica that matches the structures and forms of nature.

The basilica has three main facades: Nativity (Birth), Passion (Passion) and Glory (Glory) facades.

Nativity Facade-Depicting the birth of Jesus, this facade is decorated with natural elements and details. It

is the only facade completed during Gaudí's lifetime and reflects his love for nature.

Passion Facade - Depicting the crucifixion of Jesus, this facade is characterized by strict lines and minimal decorative details. Completed by Josep Maria Subirachs.

Glory Facade- Planned as the main entrance, this facade will depict the themes of heaven, hell and resurrection and is still unfinished.

The basilica has eighteen towers, which represent twelve apostles, four evangelists, Mary and Jesus. These towers are of different heights and rise in a spiral. The tallest tower is the tower representing the man and will reach a height of 170 meters when completed. The interior of the Sagrada Família is a beautiful synthesis of natural light and colors. When planning the interior, Gaudí specifically used stained glass windows and different colored mosaics to let the daylight enter in a spectacular way. It creates a color harmony and a spiritual atmosphere inside. The columns resemble tree trunks and make the interior of the basilica look like a forest. Gaudí used innovative structural solutions in the Sagrada Família. Known for its curved lines and parabolic arches, the basilica is also an engineering

masterpiece. Gaudí, inspired by nature, applied the structures of trees and plants in architectural design.

The Sagrada Família represents the pinnacle of Antoni Gaudí's work and is one of the most magnificent examples of modernism. With its design inspired by nature, magnificent facades and the harmony of light and color of its interior, this basilica remains a unique

pearl of world architecture. Once completed, the Sagrada Família will be both architecturally and religiously significant and will continue to convey Gaudí's ingenious ideas to future generations.

In 1984, it was included among the buildings declared as World Heritage by UNESCO under the name "Works of Antoni Gaudí".

La Sagrada Família under construction, 1887. (9) La Sagrada Família, 1915

Nativity façade in August 2017 [9].

Basilica of San Pietro

The Basilica of San Pietro is a magnificent basilica located in the heart of the Vatican and considered the center of the Catholic Church. This building occupies an important place in religious and architectural history. One of the largest and most important architectural projects of the Renaissance, the Basilica of San Pietro is also a place that visitors and worshipers flock to worldwide. The construction of the Basilica of San Pietro was started in 1506 by Pope Julius II. The construction of the basilica lasted for about 120 years and was completed in 1626. During this long period, many famous architects worked on the project, including Donato Bramante, Michelangelo, Carlo Maderno and Gian Lorenzo Bernini. The Basilica of San Pietro is the second of the four largest basilicas in Rome. It is the most prominent building in the Vatican. It is the largest church of Christianity. It is built on an area of 23,000 m² (2.3 ha) and has a capacity of 60,000 people. In front of the basilica is the two-part St. Peter's Square, and both parts of the square are surrounded by a tall colonnade. The massive columned facade of the

basilica is well visible from the end of the square, a grand staircase separates the basilica from the square. On both sides of the staircase stand 5.55 m high statues of the apostles Peter and Paul, who worked in Rome in the 1st century.

The Basilica of San Pietro was built on the site of the old Church of San Pietro from the previous IV century. This church was built by the Roman emperor Constantine and was located over the tomb of St. Peter. The decision to replace the old church with a grander and larger basilica was intended to symbolize the power and magnificence of the Catholic Church.

Compared to other churches, the interiors are huge. One of the authors who studied the church writes that "When people approach this or that monument inside the church, we feel how small and cramped they seem, and only then do we gradually realize that the building has enormous impact on humans [10]. One of the most striking architectural features of the Basilica of San Pietro is its large dome. Designed by Michelangelo, this dome is one of the largest domes in the world and occupies an important place in the

skyline of Rome. The interior and exterior of the dome are richly decorated and a magnificent view opens from the top of the dome. The facade of the basilica was designed by Carlo Maderno and completed in 1612. Wide staircases, entrance portals and huge columns of the facade amaze the visitors. At the top of the facade, there are statues of St. Peter and other saints. The interior of the Basilica of San Pietro is known for its spaciousness and rich decorations. The main nave of the basilica is notable for its high ceilings and monumental columns. The decorations, mosaics, sculptures and paintings inside are some of the best examples of the Renaissance and Baroque periods. The Baldachin (canopy), designed by Gian Lorenzo Bernini, is located over the main altar and is one of the central elements of the basilica. The basilica houses

1922

many famous statues and shrines. The "Pietà" sculpture by Michelangelo is one of the most famous works of art inside the basilica. In addition, the tomb of St. Peter and the magnificent chapels designed by Bernini add to the religious and historical importance of the basilica.

The Basilica of San Pietro occupies an irreplaceable place in architectural and religious history. As one of the most magnificent works of the Renaissance, this basilica is visited by millions of tourists and worshippers every year. The Basilica of San Pietro continues to amaze people for centuries as a monument that symbolizes the power and magnificence of the Catholic Church. St. Peter's Basilica, the most important building of the Vatican, which is of great historical and architectural importance, was included in the UNESCO World Heritage List in 1984.

2023

Conclusion

Religious architectural monuments provide valuable information about the history, culture and religious belief systems of societies. These buildings are not only places of worship, but also demonstrate the highest levels of human creativity and technical skill. In the future, the protection of religious architectural monuments and their transmission to new generations will be important.

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